

22 state-wide PPH surveys for wild turkeys provide a valuable measure of wild turkey productivity
23 that can be used to forecast future hunter harvests and population status.

24 **1. Introduction**

25 Roadside brood count surveys are commonly used to monitor populations of avian
26 species in the order Galliformes [1,2]. In general, these surveys usually include standardized
27 routes where the number of adults and juvenile individuals encountered are counted. This
28 approach can be effective for species that commonly brood in early succession communities with
29 high visibility from roads and when dimorphism between sexes and age classes is sufficient.
30 Protocols have been developed and implemented to collect relative abundance and reproductive
31 information for ruffed grouse *Bonasa umbellus* [3], sooty grouse *Dendragapus fuliginosus* [4,5]
32 sage-grouse *Centrocercus spp.* [6,7], northern bobwhite *Colinus virginianus* [8] and scaled quail
33 *Callipepla squamata* [9], Grey Partridge *Perdix perdix*, Red-legged partridge *Alectoris rufa*, Red
34 grouse *Lagopus lagopus*, and Black Grouse *Tetrao tetrix* in Europe [1]. While this approach is
35 widely used, precision in predicting population parameters may be low [10], especially without
36 adequate sampling across the area and timeframe of interest [11].

37 A unique version of the roadside brood count survey method (hereafter poult-per-hen
38 survey; PPH) has been adopted to track productivity of wild turkeys (*Meleagris gallopavo*) by
39 most U.S. states within its range [12–14]. The survey consists of counts of adult females (hens)
40 and recently hatched juvenile turkeys (i.e., poults) during the summer (July and August –
41 sometimes includes June), and this ratio is used as an index of productivity [15,16], as well as
42 various other metrics depending on the state and timeframe [12–15]. PPH was collected for
43 decades by each state using a variety of approaches (e.g., some states include observations in
44 June, some would remove less-reliable observations post-hoc, etc.). The predictive power of

45 these surveys has not been formally evaluated across states. However, Butler et al. [12] reported
46 that PPH estimates positively correlated to one-year-old male observations in the subsequent
47 year in Mississippi, USA, indicating that the PPH in that state may have been positively
48 correlated to productivity. If the PPH survey does provide a reliable prediction of adult males in
49 the future population, they would provide an important tool for testing hypotheses related to
50 broad-scale patterns in wild turkey populations [15].

51 To test whether PPH provides a useful index of turkey productivity, we combined yearly
52 PPH measurements from 14 states with the respective hunter harvest data over the same time
53 period. Wild turkeys are a popular game species, and adult males (i.e., ≥ 2 years old – hereafter
54 referred to as ‘toms’) make up most animals harvested. Moreover, 2-year-old toms often drive
55 hunter harvest numbers [17,18]. When hunter harvest of toms is weighted by hunter effort (i.e.,
56 hunter harvest index), it likely provides a strong indicator of population size [12,15,19–21].
57 Thus, if PPH provides a valuable index of productivity, it should predict the hunter harvest index
58 two years later. As such, we modeled the relationship between current PPH and hunter harvest
59 and hunter harvest index two years later.

60 **2. Methods**

61 *2.1. PPH, Hunter Harvest, and Hunter Effort Datasets*

62 We compiled wild turkey state-level PPH data and spring hunter harvest metrics from
63 U.S. state agencies that either: 1) provided the data publicly online; or 2) provided data to the
64 authors upon request (see Table S1 for specifics of data origins and Table S2 for public dataset).
65 We intentionally did not include states in our dataset that had consistently low spring wild turkey
66 hunter harvest numbers (< 5000) or states that purposefully have attempted to lower their harvest

67 numbers, so that we could reduce potential bias when exploring the potential relationship with
68 PPH. We gathered PPH and harvest data from 14 states: 1) Alabama; 2) Arkansas; 3) Florida; 4)
69 Georgia; 5) Indiana; 6) Iowa; 7) Kentucky; 8) Mississippi; 9) Missouri; 10) North Carolina; 11)
70 Ohio; 12) Pennsylvania; 13) South Carolina; and 14) Tennessee. Of these states, we were also
71 able to gather hunter effort (number of hunters) from nine states: 1) Alabama; 2) Arkansas; 3)
72 Florida; 4) Georgia; 5) Indiana; 6) Mississippi; 7) North Carolina; 8) Pennsylvania; and 9) South
73 Carolina. The complete dataset ranged from 1993-2025; for specific years included from each
74 state, please see Table S1.

75 *2.2. Data Analysis*

76 We used linear mixed-effects models to assess the following: 1) the relationship between
77 PPH data and the hunter harvest two years later (e.g., PPH data collected in 2016 predicts hunter
78 harvest in 2018); and 2) the relationship between PPH data and the hunter harvest index two years
79 later. For each model, we removed outliers from our dataset by identifying residuals that were >
80 2.5 standard deviations from zero and we included state as a random effect. We explored including
81 year as an additional random effect, but initial analysis revealed that variation was primarily
82 captured by the state from which the observation was recorded (i.e., within year variation in PPH
83 was dependent on state of observation). For the models assessing hunter harvest, we reported
84 hunter harvest as ‘number of wild turkeys harvested * 10⁻⁴’ for ease of interpretation. For the
85 models assessing hunter harvest index, we reported this index as ‘number of wild turkeys harvested
86 ÷ number of hunters participating’. For both models, we log transformed (*ln*) the dependent
87 variable because both dependent variables were highly right-skewed (see Results) and this
88 presented issues for the normality of model residuals. Analyses were conducted using R version
89 4.4.3 [22].

90 3. Results

91 3.1. Descriptive Statistics

92 PPH values ranged from 4.4 (Indiana 2004) to 0.8 (Missouri 2016 & 2017), with an
93 average value of 2.0 (± 0.6 ; $n = 165$). Annual hunter harvest varied widely depending on the
94 state, with the highest harvest recorded in our dataset being 47,084 (Alabama 2021) and the
95 lowest being 7,013 (Arkansas 2019). The overall average annual hunter harvest was 20,518 (\pm
96 9,623). The average hunter harvest index value for the dataset was 0.33 (± 0.14 ; $n = 97$),
97 meaning that nearly 1 in 3 hunters successfully harvested a wild turkey, although the real ratio is
98 smaller given that some hunters harvest multiple turkeys in a season. The hunter harvest index
99 from Alabama was consistently higher compared to other states, with the index being > 0.70 in
100 each of 4 years of Alabama data, and Alabama recorded the seven highest index values overall.
101 In contrast, the lowest hunter harvest index values were consistently from Pennsylvania, with
102 seven years of data being < 0.20 , with the lowest recorded value of 0.14.

103 3.2. Linear Mixed Effects Models

104 PPH and Hunter harvest two-years later were positively correlated ($B = 0.11$; $p < 0.001$)
105 and the conditional r^2 was 0.89 (Table 1; Figure 1). Variation of this model was strongly affected
106 by the state ($\tau_{00 \text{ State}} = 0.19$; Intraclass Correlation Coefficient [ICC] = 0.88). Using the subset of
107 the dataset with hunter harvest index data, we determined that PPH and hunter harvest index
108 two-years later were positively correlated ($B = 0.18$; $p < 0.001$) and the conditional r^2 was 0.91
109 (Figure 2). Variation of this model was strongly affected by the state ($\tau_{00 \text{ State}} = 0.19$; ICC = 0.91).

110 4. Discussion

111 Our results indicate that PPH is a strong predictor of the hunter harvest two years later
112 across states, regardless of whether hunter effort (hunter harvest index) is considered. Since
113 hunter harvest index is likely a good indicator of population size and is related to hunter
114 satisfaction [23–25], our results indicate that PPH estimates may provide a strong dataset to
115 measure productivity each year and forecast the future population status with enough time to
116 adjust hunter expectations if desirable or harvest regulations if needed. Monitoring programs are
117 often plagued with a tradeoff between sampling extent, precision and accuracy, and logistical
118 constraint. Myriad approaches have been utilized to maximize this tradeoff including advances in
119 technology as well as utilizing citizen scientists. In this case, observations from the public and
120 natural resource professionals allow data collection at a scale to provide useful estimates of
121 productivity through PPH that potentially predict future population indices.

122 Wild turkey populations and productivity may have declined in some regions recently
123 and PPH data provides a strong opportunity to test hypotheses [15]. For example, Byrne et al.
124 [15] used the PPH data across Southeastern states to propose that recent turkey declines may be a
125 density dependent response following a period of intrinsic population growth rates after
126 restocking efforts. They supported this hypothesis using trends in statewide PPH data as a basis
127 for inference. Similarly, Butler et al. [12] used PPH data to evaluate changes to hunting season
128 frameworks in Mississippi, USA and also noted that PPH successfully predicted subsequent one
129 year old male abundance in the following year. Our results indicate that PPH surveys may have
130 utility across a larger geographic extent and over longer time periods, despite clear separation in
131 productivity and harvest metrics based on regionality. We suggest that PPH provides a strong
132 opportunity to evaluate several other factors that may be of immediate importance to the status of
133 wild turkeys [26,27]. For example, PPH could be used to evaluate the effectiveness of shifts in

134 hunting season policies such as changes to timing and bag limits [28]. Since policies are
135 regulated at the state level, and states usually do not change policies in the same way in the same
136 years across states, the natural experimental design would resemble a robust before-after control-
137 impact design since PPH could be compared before and after policies were changed in some
138 states and not others [29]. Similarly, there is strong evidence that insect populations and
139 insectivores have declined across the range of wild turkeys [30,31]. Insects are the most
140 important food source for juvenile wild turkeys (poults) and an increase or decrease in insect
141 abundance could have strong implications for wild turkey productivity [32,33]. For example,
142 anecdotally, many have indicated that surges in insect abundance during periodical cicada
143 (*Magicicada* spp.) have increased wild turkey productivity [34,35]. The PPH dataset could be
144 used to determine if turkey productivity is insect limited by measuring how PPH responds to
145 insect additions, such as those that occur with periodical cicada emergences. These emergences
146 are mostly prevalent in the eastern United States, which coincides with the most historical
147 collection of PPH data.

148 PPH, hunter harvest, and the hunter harvest index are either estimated or determined
149 using online harvest reporting, citizen science efforts, and hunter surveys. Yet, to date, little
150 research has been conducted assessing participation in these initiatives, particularly assessing
151 which members of the public are less likely to participate, what motivates individuals to
152 participate, and how invested public citizens are in the data generated from these initiatives.
153 While broadly speaking there is a growing need for more wild turkey human dimensions
154 research [36], specifically human dimensions efforts that explore participation in summer brood
155 surveys in states that rely on citizen science or combined efforts to generate their PPH data is
156 crucial. Understanding the motivations and barriers to participating in summer brood surveys

157 could be used to increase participation and better streamline the resources for reporting
158 observations. Examining how and to what degree the public uses PPH data, especially at smaller
159 scales (e.g., PPH for the different districts in Alabama, USA) may reveal if this is an important
160 component of a hunter's decision-making process (i.e., are some hunters targeting different areas
161 of the state depending on smaller-scale PPH and harvest data).

162 Importantly, the difference in how states determine or estimate hunter harvest, and the
163 methodology of estimating PPH is a limitation of our research. In 2019, the National Wild
164 Turkey Federation (NWTF) Technical Committee consisting of wild turkey coordinators across
165 states, developed a standardized summer brood survey protocol. This protocol was developed
166 after these inconsistencies were highlighted by Byrne et al. [37] to the Southeastern Association
167 of Fish and Wildlife Agencies' Wild Turkey Working Group [38]. The standardization was
168 intended to ensure surveys were comparable across states such that regional scale monitoring and
169 comparisons of productivity would be facilitated. The new standardized protocol implemented
170 the removal of the following observations prior to finalizing PPH data [39]: 1) Where $\geq 25\%$ of
171 the turkeys were marked as unidentified/unknown; 2) where ≥ 8 hens were without poults; 3)
172 where poults were seen without hens; 4) where ≥ 1 poult and ≥ 1 hen were seen in which the
173 ratio of poults to hens is ≥ 16 , or where the ratio of hens to poults is ≤ 0.0625 ; 5) where the
174 turkeys seen were believed to have been previously recorded; and 6) those conducted outside of
175 a 01-July – 31-August time window. We did not separately analyze PPH from updated protocols
176 because of the lack of data accumulated since this change (only 2019-2025) and because much of
177 the publicly available online data does not appear to be reported using the updated protocols.
178 Even so, our analysis shows that historical data are useful to test hypotheses over longer time

179 periods, but the newly standardized protocol will likely strengthen the value of the PPH data set
180 for future work.

181 Even with these updated protocols, some additional standardization may increase the
182 accuracy and precision of the PPH estimates. For example, standardizing or otherwise tracking
183 sampling effort, especially across the subunits being managed within states, would allow
184 estimates of PPH and other measurements to be contextualized based on sampling effort
185 strengthening the inferential power. In Kansas, a similar approach is used to track the
186 populations of turkeys and pheasants, where agency personnel use permanent brood routes that
187 were randomly selected and positioned to be representative of typical land cover for that region,
188 while controlling for timing and quantity of data collection [40]. This may be important given
189 that factors influencing populations may differ across subunits and statewide PPH metrics may
190 be skewed to represent biases in sampling effort where it is concentrated in those subunits. We
191 note that one of the states in our analysis may have reflected this pattern. In Florida, the sampling
192 effort for PPH was concentrated in the northern part of the state, whereas hunter harvest effort
193 was more representative of the southern part of the state. Given the northern and southern parts
194 of the state are different subspecies and climates (*M.g. silvestris* and subtropical in North; *M.g.*
195 *Osceola* and tropical in the South; [41]), it is possible that sampling bias in PPH may have
196 weakened its predictive power of the statewide harvest if productivity across the state varied
197 from year to year. It may not be practical to standardize or even track sampling effort, but
198 stratifying sampling and inferences at smaller scales would likely improve the inferential power
199 of PPH when possible. In addition, weighting the influence of summer brood survey
200 observations in regions with high participation but historically low turkey abundance may be
201 necessary to limit potential bias, although this needs to be explored further.

202 Overall, our findings indicate that the PPH is a useful data set to monitor turkey
203 productivity that can be used to test hypotheses at a large spatiotemporal scale. While our dataset
204 includes many of the Southeastern and Midwestern states with a long and rich history of wild
205 turkey hunting and management, this resulted in our research almost exclusively focusing on
206 *M.g. silvestris* (excluding the Florida data that includes *M.g. Osceola*). Future efforts should
207 attempt to expand the geographic range of data so that more wild turkey subspecies are included.
208 Similarity, by expanding the range of data, social, cultural, and management differences can also
209 be accounted for that may also influence the relationship between PPH and hunting metrics two
210 years later. We recommend that additional changes be adopted to further strengthen the data set
211 such as: 1) standardized routes that are replicated within the year or across years; 2) intentional
212 stratification of sampling effort across space and time each year; and 3) weighting observations
213 based upon regional size, human population, or other factors that may influence observations.

214 **Acknowledgements**

215 We would like to thank the following state agencies for kindly providing turkey hunting data
216 either via personal email or by making this data publicly available on their website: Alabama
217 Department of Conservation and Natural Resources, Arkansas Game and Fish Commission,
218 Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, Georgia Department of Natural Resources
219 – Wildlife Resources Division, Indiana Department of Natural Resources – Division of Fish &
220 Wildlife, Iowa Department of Natural Resources, Kentucky Department of Fish & Wildlife,
221 Mississippi Wildlife, Fisheries, and Parks, Missouri Department of Conservation, North Carolina
222 Wildlife Resources Commission, Ohio Department of Natural Resources – Division of Wildlife,
223 Pennsylvania Game Commission, South Carolina Department of Natural Resources, and
224 Tennessee Wildlife Resources Agency. Please see Table S1 for more specific details.

225 **Ethical statement**

226 This research was conducted using previously recorded datasets gathered by U.S. state agencies
227 (see Table S1 and Table S2) and was approved under the University of Florida Research
228 Division of Research Operations (Protocol #NH00048066).

229 **Funding Statement**

230 This research was partly funded by the University of Florida's Institute of Food and Agricultural
231 Sciences.

232 **Data Accessibility**

233 Datasets used for this research were gathered using both publicly available data listed on U.S.
234 state agency websites and via personal communication with agency personnel. As such, we are
235 able to provide the publicly available data (see Table S2), but data that was provided by agency
236 personnel (see Table S1) cannot be included.

237 **Competing Interests**

238 We have no competing interests to report.

239 **References**

- 240 1. Aebischer NJ, Baines D. 2008. Monitoring gamebird abundance and productivity in the UK: The
241 GWCT long-term datasets. *Rev. Catalana Ornitol.* **24**, 30–43.
- 242 2. Sands JP, Pope MD. 2010. A survey of galliform monitoring programs and methods in the United
243 States and Canada. *Wildl. Biol.* **16**, 342–356.
- 244 3. Ammann GA, Ryel LA. 1963. Extensive methods of inventorying ruffed grouse in Michigan. *J.*
245 *Wildl. Manage.* **27**, 617–633.
- 246 4. Zwickel FC. 1958. Fall studies of forest-grouse in northcentral Washington. MS Thesis. State
247 College of Washington, Pullman, Washington, USA.
- 248 5. Zwickel FC. (1990). Blue grouse. In: *Handbook of census methods for terrestrial vertebrates* (ed.
249 Davis DE), pp. 63-65. Boca Raton, Florida, USA: CRC Press, Inc.
- 250 6. Dalke PD, Pyrah DB., Stanton DC, Crawford JE, Schlatterer EF. 1963. Ecology, productivity,
251 and management of sage grouse in Idaho. *J. Wildl. Manage.* **27**, 811–841.
- 252 7. Patterson RL. 1952. The sage grouse in the upper Green River Basin of Wyoming. PhD
253 Dissertation. University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Michigan, USA.
- 254 8. Schwartz CC. 1974. Analysis of survey data collected on bobwhite in Iowa. *J. Wildl. Manage.* **38**,
255 674–678.
- 256 9. Hoffman DM. 1965. The scaled quail in Colorado: range, population status, harvest. Publication
257 No 21 – State of Colorado, Department of Game, Fish and Parks, Denver, Colorado, USA.
- 258 10. Rice CG. 2003. Utility of pheasant call counts and brood counts for monitoring
259 population density and predicting harvest. *West. N. Am. Nat.* **63**, 178–188.
- 260 11. Anderson GL. 1983. Evaluation of sharp-tailed grouse, ring-necked pheasant, and gray partridge
261 surveys in North Dakota. MS Thesis. North Dakota State University, Fargo, North Dakota, USA.

- 262 12. Butler AB, Wang G, Godwin KD. 2015. Using avid hunter and brood surveys to predict hunter
263 success and assess regulatory changes in spring gobbler seasons. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp*
264 **11**, 225–235.
- 265 13. Roberts SD, Porter WF. 1998. Influence of temperature and precipitation on survival of wild
266 turkey poults. *J. Wildl. Manage.* **62**, 1499–1505.
- 267 14. Vangilder LD, Kurzejeski EW. 1995. Population ecology of the eastern wild turkey in northern
268 Missouri. *Wildl. Monogr.* **130**, 1–50.
- 269 15. Byrne ME, Chamberlain MJ, Collier BA. 2015. Potential density dependence in wild turkey
270 productivity in the Southeastern United States. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp* **11**, 329–351.
- 271 16. Bowling AC, Williams DM, Parent CJ, Porter WF, Schiavone MV, Swift BL. 2015. Brooding
272 over broods: regional impacts of habitat quality on wild turkey productivity. *Proc. Natl. Wild*
273 *Turkey Symp.* **11**, 315–328.
- 274 17. Miller DA, Chamberlain MJ, Leopold BD, Hurst, GA. 2000. Lessons from Tallahala: what have
275 we learned for turkey management into the 21st Century?. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp* **8**, 23–
276 33.
- 277 18. Wightman PH et al. 2024. Survival and cause-specific mortality of male wild turkeys across the
278 southeastern United States. *J. Wildl. Manage.* **88**, e22531.
- 279 19. Kurzejeski EW, Vangilder LD. 1992. Population management. In: *The wild turkey:*
280 *biology and management* (ed. Dickson JW) pp 165-184. Harrisburg, Pennsylvania, USA:
281 Stackpole Books.
- 282 20. Lint JR, Leopold BD, Hurst GA. 1995. Comparison of abundance indexes and population
283 estimates for wild turkey gobblers. *Wildl. Soc. Bull.* **23**, 164–168.
- 284 21. Wang G, Butler AB, Shan X. 2023. Inverse relationships between coyote and wild turkey
285 population time series: Implications for future studies of predator–prey interactions. *Wildl. Lett.* **1**,
286 171–177.

- 287 22. R Core Team. 2025. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. R Foundation
288 for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria.
- 289 23. Bishir J, Lancia RA. 1996. On catch-effort methods of estimating animal abundance. *Biometrics*
290 **52**, 1457–1466.
- 291 24. Parent CJ, Stevens BS, Bowling AC, Porter WF. 2015. Wild turkey harvest trends across the
292 Midwest in the 21st century. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp* **11**, 211–223.
- 293 25. Wynveen CJ, Cavin DA, Wright BA, Hammitt WE. 2005. Determinants of a quality wild turkey
294 hunting season. *Environ. Manage.* **36**, 117–124.
- 295 26. Sibiya M, Goldstein BR, Pacifici K, Kays R, Cove MV, Jensen AJ, McShea WJ, Mason BM,
296 Callaghan CT, Lashley MA, Baruzzi C. In-Press. Assessing spatial ecological patterns of wild
297 turkey relative abundance across North America. *Wildl. Soc. Bull.* (In-Press).
- 298 27. Sibiya M, Mason BM, Baruzzi C, Bowler DE, Lashley MA, Callaghan CT. In-Press. Data
299 integration reveals that a statewide corridor initiative maintains greater wild turkey relative
300 abundance and occupancy. *Landsc. Ecol.* (In-Press).
- 301 28. Quehl JO, Phillips LM, Johnson VM, Harper CA, Clark JD, Shields RD, Buehler DA. 2024.
302 Assessing wild turkey productivity before and after a 14-day delay in the start date of the spring
303 hunting season in Tennessee. *Ecol. Evol.* **14**, e11390.
- 304 29. Thiault L, Kernaléguen L, Osenberg CW, Claudet J. 2017. Progressive-change BACIPS: A
305 flexible approach for environmental impact assessment. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* **8**, 288–296.
- 306 30. Bossart JL, Carlton CE. 2002. Insect conservation in America: status and perspectives. *Am.*
307 *Entomol.* **48**, 82–92.
- 308 31. Wagner DL. 2020. Insect declines in the Anthropocene. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* **65**, 457–480.
- 309 32. Peoples JC, Sisson DC, Speake DW. 1995. Wild turkey brood habitat use and characteristics in
310 coastal plain pine forests. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp* **7**, 89–96.
- 311 33. Metzler R, Speake DW. 1985. Wild turkey poult mortality rates and their relationship to brood
312 habitat structure in northeast Alabama. *Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp* **5**, 103–112.

- 313 34. Backs SE. 2005. Wild turkey brood production – summer 2004. Management and Research Note
314 #891. Indiana Division of Fish and Wildlife, Indianapolis, IN, USA.
- 315 35. Backs SE, McCallen E. 2021. Wild turkey summer brood production indices – 2021.
316 Management and Research Note #2067. Indiana Department of Natural Resources, Indianapolis,
317 IN USA.
- 318 36. Steele ZT, Lashley MA. In-Press. Reviewing human dimensions of wild turkey hunting research
319 and synthesizing future directions. *Wildl. Soc. Bull. (Proc. Natl. Wild Turkey Symp)*. (In-Press).
- 320 37. Byrne ME, Chamberlain MJ, Collier BA. 2014. A Retrospective regional analysis of wild turkey
321 productivity in the Southeast. A report submitted to the Southeast Association of Fish and
322 Wildlife Agencies Wild Turkey Working Group.
- 323 38. Wood J. 2024. Standardizing summer brood surveys. National Wild Turkey Federation,
324 Edgefield, South Carolina, USA.
- 325 39. Oakley N. 2024. 2024 Missouri wild turkey brood survey results. Missouri Department of
326 Conservation, Columbia, Missouri, USA.
- 327 40. Prendergast J. 2024. Quail, pheasant, & turkey brood survey – 2024. Kansas Department of
328 Wildlife, Parks, and Tourism, Pratt, Kansas, USA.
- 329 41. McDougal D. 2023. Behind the bird: history and conservation of the Osceola wild turkey.
330 National Wild Turkey Federation, Edgefield, South Carolina, USA.

331 **Table 1.** Results of linear mixed effects models using wild turkey poult-per-hen (PPH) from two years
 332 prior to predict: 1) wild turkey hunter harvest ($\times 10^{-4}$; 14 states); and 2) wild turkey hunter harvest index
 333 (hunter harvest \div number of hunters; 9 states). Both dependent variables were log transformed (\ln).

Item	<i>B</i>	S.E.	t-value	p-value
<i>ln(Hunter harvest)</i>				
Intercept	0.448	0.134	3.330	0.003
PPH (poult-per-hen)	0.113	0.032	3.579	< 0.001
Marginal r^2	0.02			
Conditional r^2	0.89			
Observations	165			
n_{State}	14			
Between-group variance (state)	0.19			
Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC)	0.88			
<i>ln(Hunter harvest index)</i>				
Intercept	-1.460	0.163	-8.986	< 0.001
PPH	0.176	0.037	4.705	< 0.001
Marginal r^2	0.05			
Conditional r^2	0.91			
Observations	97			
n_{State}	9			
Between-group variance (state)	0.19			

ICC

0.91

335

336 **Figure 1.** General trendlines demonstrating the relationship between wild turkey poult-per-hen

337 (PPH) data and hunter harvest ($*10^{-4}$) for each individual state included in the dataset.

338

339 **Figure 2.** General trendlines demonstrating the relationship between wild turkey poult-per-hen
 340 (PPH) data and the hunter harvest index (number of wild turkeys harvested ÷ number of wild
 341 turkey hunter) for each individual state included in the dataset.